

Acknowledgement

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Potential Tuberculostats : Some Products from Malonanilic Acid Hydrazides

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ACID hydrazides and their condensation products have gained prominence as tuberculostatic¹, anti-fungal², antileprotic³ and antihelmintic⁴ agents. Buu-Hoi⁵ *et al* have synthesised a large number of hydrazides and their condensation products with various aldehydes and ketones in view of the possibility of their being less toxic than parent hydrazides due to blocking of the free -NH₂ group. A careful literature review has revealed that condensation of fluorine bearing aldehyde with acid hydrazides of malonanilic acid series has not been done so far. Organic compounds having fluorine have shown promise in different fields. The present study records the condensation of *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde with malonanilic acid hydrazides in ethanol and formation of acid hydrazones of the type I.

I

The identity of the products (I) has been established by the elemental analysis and ir spectra.

The ir spectrum of acid hydrazone (I ; R = H) shows absorption band of C=N group at 1600 cm⁻¹, N-N group at 1240 cm⁻¹, NH-CO group

at 1630 cm⁻¹ and -CH₂ group at 1440 cm⁻¹ and the band at 780 cm⁻¹ confirms *p*-substitution.

Iminophosphinic acids have been found to possess anticancerous properties⁶. In order to study the effect of substituents on physiological activity, three new iminophosphinic acids of type II have been synthesised by the treatment of acid hydrazones(I) with hypophosphorous acid.

II

Oxadiazole moiety is associated with many interesting biological properties and malonanilic acid hydrazides have been scrutinized for antitubercular activity. New compounds (III) have been obtained in which two moieties have been fused for the first time by the condensation of 5-phenyl-2-chloroacetamido-1,3,4-oxadiazole with malonanilic acid hydrazides and the products of the type III have been obtained in low yield.

III

Experimental

Malonanilic acid hydrazides were prepared according to the procedure reported in the literature⁷.

Condensation of p-fluorobenzaldehyde with malonanilic acid hydrazone : (I ; R = H)

General method : Solutions of *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.124 g ; 0.001 mole) in absolute ethanol (1.0 ml) and malonanilic acid hydrazone (0.193 g ; 0.001 mole) in ethanol (3.0 ml) were mixed and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. The mixture was gently boiled for two minutes. On cooling the product separated. Crystallisation from ethanol gave shining silky needles of the acid hydrazone. Yield : 0.23 g (76.9%) m.p. 218° ; Found : N, 14.47 ; F, 6.58%. C₁₆H₁₄O₂N₃F requires N, 14.05 ; F, 6.23%.

Reaction of malonanilic acid hydrazone of p-fluorobenzaldehyde with hypophosphorous acid : (II ; R = H)

General method : Acid hydrazone (0.299 g ; 0.001 mole) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (10 ml) and hypophosphorous acid (2.0 g.) was added. Mixture was gently heated for five minutes and set aside for ten minutes. On cooling white solid separated out, which was collected under suction and recrystallised from ethanol in white shining crystals. Yield : 0.25 g (69.3%) m.p. 147° ; Found : N, 11.10 ; F, 5.60%. C₁₆H₁₇O₄N₃FP requires N, 11.50 ; F, 5.20%.

* For correspondence.

Condensation of 5-phenyl-2-chloroacetamido-1,3,4-oxadiazole with malonanilic acid hydrazide: (III; R=H)

General method: To a solution of 2-chloroacetamido-5-phenyl-oxadiazole (0.235 g; 0.001 mole) in absolute ethanol (20.0 ml), ethanolic solution of the acid hydrazide (0.285 g; 0.001 mole), pyridine (0.23 ml) and dimethyl formamide (0.2 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for ten hrs, ethanol was distilled off and the residue was washed successively with water and hot ethanol. The product was obtained as white crystals.

Yield: 0.11 g, (28.1%) m.p. 240°; Found: N, 21.28%. C₁₉H₁₈O₄N₆ requires N, 21.32%.

Biological activity: Biological activities of the new products are under investigation and shall be reported elsewhere.

TABLE I

Sl No.	Compound R I	m.p. °C	Yield %
1.	-H	218	76.9
2.	-Cl(o)	190	73.4
3.	-Cl(m)	215	38.9
4.	-Cl(p)	231	77.9
5.	-CH ₃ (o)	226	38.5
6.	-CH ₃ (m)	221	67.09
7.	-CH ₃ (p)	210	71.7
8.	-OCH ₃ (o)	230	57.70
9.	-OCH ₃ (m)	202	59.2
10.	-OCH ₃ (p)	225	57.90
R II			
1.	-H	147	69.30
2.	-Cl(p)	155	87.50
3.	-OH ₂ (p)	192	84.21
R III			
1.	-H	240	28.10
2.	-Cl(o)	227	18.20
3.	-Cl(m)	236	18.20
4.	-Cl(p)	232	18.20
5.	-CH ₃ (o)	238	14.03
6.	-CH ₃ (m)	236	12.70
7.	-CH ₃ (p)	235	12.70

Compound R I = Acid Hydrazones.

Compound R II = Iminophosphinic Acids.

Compound R III = N-(5-Phenyl-1,3,4-Oxadiazolo)-malon-unsusbstituted/substituted-aniloyl-hydrazino acetamides.

All the products are white crystalline solids and gave satisfactory results of analysis.

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Chemical Constituents of *Elaeocarpus sikkimensis* Leaves

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Elaeocarpus sikkimensis (Family-*Elaeocarpaceae*) grows in the eastern Himalayas and in the hills of Sikkim and Assam upto a height of 5000 ft. In view of the medicinal uses of *E. ganitrus* and related species in the traditional system of medicine¹, several *Elaeocarpus* species have been investigated in our laboratory²⁻⁷ and in the present communication the chemical constituents of *E. sikkimensis* are reported.

Experimental

The air-dried and powdered leaves of the plant were extracted with ethanol (95%), the concentrated extract was adsorbed on paper pulp and extracted successively with petrol (60-80°), ether and ethyl acetate. The petrol extract on column chromatography over Al₂O₃ column yielded compound A and B. The ether extract on column chromatography over SiO₂ yielded compounds C, D and E and ethyl acetate extract yielded compound F.

Compound A was identified as β -sitosterol, m.p. 138° (acetate, m.p. 124°). The crystalline compound B, m.p. 288-89°, on acid hydrolysis furnished glucose (PC) and β -sitosterol (m.m.p., Co-TLC). Direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-TLC) with authentic sample established identity of the compound with β -sitosterol-D-glucoside⁸. Compound C, C₁₅H₁₀O₆ (M⁺, 286), m.p. 272-73°; λ_{max} 268, 368 nm (tetraacetate, m.p. 176-78°) was identified as kaempferol⁹. Compound D, C₁₅H₁₀O₇, m.p. 312°; λ_{max} 268, 272 nm furnished a penta methylether (M⁺, 372), m.p. 151°. Its identity with quercetin was settled by direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-TLC) with reference sample (Sigma). Compound E, C₇H₆O₆, m.p. 248° was recognised as gallic acid (triacetate, m.p. 163°) by direct comparison with authentic sample (E. Merck).

Compound F, crystallised from pyridine as straw-coloured needles, C₁₄H₆O₈, m.p. 350°; λ_{max}